

AN EVALUATION OF BREAST CANCER-RELATED KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS

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Abstract

Background: Breast cancer is the most common malignancy affecting women worldwide and a leading cause of mortality. In Pakistan, one in nine women is at risk, with a large proportion of cases diagnosed at advanced stages due to poor awareness, cultural barriers, and inadequate screening practices. Nursing students, as future healthcare providers, play a vital role in promoting awareness and early detection strategies, yet their knowledge, attitude, and practices remain underexplored.

Aim: The study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice of female undergraduate nursing students regarding breast cancer at nursing colleges in Lahore, Pakistan.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 133 female undergraduate nursing students selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected using an adopted structured questionnaire assessing knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) related to breast cancer. Descriptive statistics, including frequency distributions and percentages, were applied using SPSS version 23 to analyze the data.

Results: Findings revealed that 45.1% of participants had low knowledge, 24.1% had moderate knowledge, and 30.8% demonstrated high knowledge about breast cancer. Attitudes were mixed, with 54.1% showing positive attitudes while 45.9% reflected negative attitudes influenced by cultural and religious beliefs. Practices were suboptimal, with only 30.8% performing breast self-examination and 25.6% undergoing clinical breast examination. Barriers included lack of knowledge, embarrassment, and misconceptions about the disease.

Conclusion: The study concluded that knowledge and practices toward breast cancer among nursing students were inadequate, despite generally positive attitudes. Targeted educational interventions, skill-based training, and culturally sensitive awareness strategies are essential to strengthen their role in breast cancer prevention and early detection.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is referred to as a dangerous growth that starts in the breast tissue and may spread to other body sections, although benign breast lumps are noncancerous growths that cannot produce the disease and are not life-threatening (Ely & Vioral, 2019). Risk factors are the conditions or behaviors that aggravate the possibility of contracting an illness on the other hand awareness is the level of knowledge and understanding individuals have concerning the health condition. Attitude does concern with beliefs or perceptions that determine health related responses and practice is the action of applying knowledge and actions toward breast cancer prevention, detection or management (Youssif, et al., 2023). Nursing students as prospective providers of healthcare must have accurate knowledge of these factors to encourage early diagnosis and prevention (Mohebi, et al., 2023).

The prevalence of breast cancer is increasing globally and it is noted to be the most diagnosed women cancer with current data estimating that there are about 2.1 million new cases recorder each year with a projection of over 3.2 million cases per year in year 2050 (Sarker et al., 2022). It is the cause of 24.2 % of all new cancers in women and the cause of most nearly 15 percent of all cancer related deaths in females around the world (Al-Mousa et al., 2020). In Pakistan, the prevalence of breast cancer is around one in 9 females and 90,000 and 40,000 new cases and deaths reported every year (Ullah et al., 2021). In low- and middle-income countries, most cases are identified at advanced stages since there is low awareness, a lack of screening programs, and cultural factors obstruct the proper detection of cancer (Odhiambo & Hunter, 2023).

The specific causes of breast cancer have not been established, but there is a list of both non-modifiable and modifiable risk factors that contribute to developing the disease. These are early age of menarche and late menopause, old age, genetic changes, exposure to radiation, hormone therapy, taking oral contraceptives, obesity, alcohol use, physical inactivity and dense breast tissue (Alshahrani et al., 2019). Nurses and nursing students should be well versed with these factors so that they can counsel and educate women in their areas of jurisdiction regarding prevention (Ferreira et al., 2020). The

proper identification of risk factors and timely detection of warning signs are the essential factors in mitigating morbidity and mortality in breast cancer (Al Thoubaity, 2019).

Early detection of breast cancer may be achieved by knowledge of breast cancer symptoms and how to conduct self-examinations, including breast self-examination (BSE), clinical breast examination (CBE), and mammography. The lack of awareness, especially in the developing world, leads many women to be misinformed about these methods, which has a negative effect on diagnosis and survival chances (Mohebi et al., 2023). The undergraduate nursing student population is a critical population group for intercession since they are ideally situated to be able to spread evidence-based information to patients and the communities in which they live (Sydora et al., 2023). Nursing education, therefore, needs to reinforce the need of awakening and screening activities in determining the future of professional practice and patient advocacy (Kaur et al., 2025).

Culturally and socially, there are factors that create obstacles to breast cancer prevention and control guiding women not to undergo screening and instead engage in confidential discussions about the topic of breast health (Ferreira et al., 2020). In most communities, breast cancer is stigmatized, spawning the fear, concealment, and overdependence of informal convictions instead of evidence-based medical treatment (Citron, 2022). These cultural elements are late in diagnosing and treating it, which leads to the fact that the fatal outcome is difficult to reverse, particularly in areas with already scarce healthcare supplies (Ortiz-Calvo et al., 2022). Nursing students should be educated to learn how to find their way around these cultural problems and support early detection and prevention (Chamberlain, 2022).

Breast cancer is not just an issue of the medical inferiority but psychosocial and educational subject. A high proportion of younger women with breast cancer are characterized by rapid disease progression, second-time metastasis, and an increased likelihood of mortality because not all of them are diagnosed in a timely manner (Dybciak et al., 2022). It is reasonable to assume that increasing the level of education among nursing students with regard to breast cancer signs and ways of screening would help to intervene

in time, decrease the burden of the disease and improve outcomes in terms of survival (Lin et al., 2021). Moreover, by establishing good habits during the period of adolescence and early adulthood, female nursing students can become role models to positively influence their living environments as well as patient communities in the community in the future (Merino et al., 2024).

This paper on knowledge, attitude and practice of breast cancer among undergraduate nurses provides essential information that is lacking in found in literature. All in all, apart from general awareness studies, little research has been done on nursing students that will be directly involved with health education, screening promotion and patient support (Ismail & Ismail, 2024). Nurses are the primary point of contact in the healthcare systems and they might maintain critical roles in educating the community, upholding the patient morally as well as inspiring them to comply through screening and treatment (Abdoli et al., 2024). The research is intended to determine the level of knowledge, attitudes and practices among undergraduate nursing learners to facilitate superior quality care, superior patient education and increased cancer prevention interventions (Applebaum et al., 2024).

Methodology

The study was done with the aim of determining the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of undergraduate nursing students as regards to breast cancer. Cross-sectional research design was used because it enables data to be collected at a particular one time in order to test current knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the participants. The study was conducted in the department of nursing at Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan as the study site. The total population of the study consisted of all undergraduate female nursing students in their 2nd, 3rd and 4th year of the nursing degree program. Male students as well as those in the 1st year were not allowed to take part.

Data Collection

The method of purposeful sampling was employed since it was necessary to select people by a set of criteria defined by the inclusion criteria. The calculation of sample size applied Slovin formula at a

95% degree of certainty with a 5 percent margin of error, which gave a required sample size of 133 students out of a total population of 200. Knowledge, attitude as well as practice in relation to breast cancer were used as mainly defined variables. The structured questionnaire used to collect the data was borrowed or adapted by Yusuf, Okafor, Olubodun, and Onigbogi (2022). The instrument had four pages of demographic data, the items related to knowledge, attitude-based questions, and practice-based behaviors. Prior to the collection of data, informed consent was signed and approval to conduct granted by the institutional authorities. The relevant respondents will be provided with assurance of confidentiality and voluntary participation after which questionnaires will be distributed.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the version 23 of SPSS. The categorical variables were presented in terms of descriptive statistics like frequencies, percentages, and various tables. The normalcy of the data was established, and reliability and validity of the instrument was determined to apply locally. A Graphical representation of data like trend distributions (histogram diagrams) and bar charts were created to help in the easier understanding of the results. Ethical considerations were maintained throughout the research process. The participants were clarified of the purpose of the study, privacy and confidentiality were informed, and the rights of withdrawal of consent were given at any point without any repercussions. There was no possibility that it would cause harm to participants and the research work was carried out in an academic nature to build on the benefit of nursing studies and awareness about breast cancer.

Results and Analysis

The demographics indicate that most of the respondents were aged 23-25 years, which means they are in their advanced years of their undergraduate course. The high percentage (44.4%) represented the third year, which implies levels of nursing education and/or exposure to clinical issues. The overwhelming majority were unmarried (94%), attributable to the young age at which the participants more likely attend undergraduate nursing programs. Few percent (1.5) of

them had a personal history of breast mass, and 8.3 had a family history of cancer, and a low exposure to cancer-related risks personal and family-wise could be extrapolated upon. In general, the demographic factors state that the sample is quite homogenous in

terms of being a group of young, unmarried nursing students that might affect their views on and approaches to breast cancer. [Table 1].

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (n = 133)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age	20–22 years	61	45.9
	23–25 years	68	51.1
	26–28 years	4	3.0
Academic Year	2nd Year	22	16.5
	3rd Year	59	44.4
	4th Year	52	39.1
Marital Status	Married	8	6.0
	Unmarried	125	94.0
History of Breast Mass	Yes	2	1.5
	No	131	98.5
Family History of Cancer	Yes	11	8.3
	No	122	91.7

The knowledge survey indicates the uneven awareness of nursing students with the media and books being the main source of information, conferences and seminars the least apart, there is no formal academic exposure. In line with knowledge gaps, 26.3 percent of students confessed not knowing about risk factors of breast cancer, which should not be the case as they will be in the field of healthcare in the future. There was disparity in awareness of the symptoms where swelling of the armpit (24.8%) stood out as the most common whereas other very important symptoms such as discharge nipple

(16.5%) and lump (18%) were not well reported with sufficient clinical awareness. Treatment awareness was small, with chemotherapy (32.3%) and radiotherapy (28.6%) accounting as the most selected variants, and yet 21.1 percent still responded with “I don’t know.” The results indicate that the low knowledge was quite general, overall nearly one-half of the students (45.1%) were poorly aware, and it indicates the necessity to invest in the breast cancer education particularly within the nursing curriculum to improve the preparation to work with patients and early detection practice. [Table 2].

Table 2: Knowledge of Undergraduate Nurses Regarding Breast Cancer

Knowledge Variable	Response Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Source of Information	Books	32	24.1
	Lectures	29	21.8
	Media	35	26.3
	Hospital	30	22.6
	Conference/Seminar	7	5.3
Risk Factors	Old age	27	20.3
	Smoking	28	21.1
	Alcohol	23	17.3
	Family history	20	15.0
	I don’t know	35	26.3
Symptoms	Breast mass	24	18.0

	Swelling under armpit	33	24.8
	Pain in the breast	28	21.1
	Nipple discharge	22	16.5
	Weight loss	26	19.5
Treatment Options	Surgery	24	18.0
	Radiotherapy	38	28.6
	Chemotherapy	43	32.3
	I don't know	28	21.1
Benefits of Early Detection	Reduce risk of death	27	20.3
	Early treatment	39	29.3
	Improve quality of life	39	29.3
	Reduce treatment cost	3	2.3
	Improve outcomes	25	18.8
Overall Knowledge	Low	60	45.1
	Moderate	32	24.1
	High	41	30.8

The chart shows that most participants recognized early treatment (29.3%) and improved quality of life (29.3%) as the key benefits of early detection. Fewer acknowledged reduced risk of death (20.3%),

improved outcomes (18.8%), and very few saw reduced treatment cost (2.3%) as major benefits.[Figure 1].

The results of the attitude questions indicate that the majority of students (54.1%) possessed a positive attitude towards breast cancer; nevertheless,

misconceptions and cultural barriers are still quite high. A number of them were embarrassed to screen and received cultural shame with screenings and 26.3 % felt it is only female doctors who should give examinations. Fatalistic approaches were also

maintained by some, with reasons that it is better not to know about cancer or employing nothing but prayers and traditional medicine. Even though the majority would disagree with the view that breast cancer is not serious, there is a certain degree of indecisiveness and indifference in answers which

show a lack of confidence and knowledge. In general, 45.9 percent still showed negative attitudes and therefore, more needs to be done in terms of influencing awareness and attitude towards it. [Table 3].

Table 3: Attitude of Undergraduate Nurses Towards Breast Cancer

Attitude Item	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Screening not necessary for all females	39.1%	15.0%	25.6%	15.8%	4.5%
Breast cancer exam is embarrassing	13.5%	23.3%	31.6%	18.8%	12.8%
Better not to know about cancer	49.6%	13.5%	12.0%	21.8%	3.0%
I can never have breast cancer	17.3%	21.8%	28.6%	20.3%	12.0%
Don't believe in screening methods	20.3%	18.8%	37.6%	16.5%	6.8%
Breast screening not culturally acceptable	30.1%	36.8%	10.5%	14.3%	8.3%
Will not screen due to religious beliefs	26.3%	25.6%	27.1%	14.3%	6.8%
Only pray if abnormality found	50.4%	19.5%	12.0%	9.8%	8.3%
Immoral to touch own breast	39.1%	21.8%	12.8%	17.3%	9.0%
Too young to have cancer	41.4%	18.0%	13.5%	18.8%	8.3%
Traditional medicine better than modern	41.4%	18.0%	13.5%	18.8%	8.3%
Breast cancer diagnosis is a death sentence	15.0%	25.6%	29.3%	22.6%	7.5%
Breast cancer not serious	54.1%	26.3%	12.8%	6.8%	0%
Women should be pitied not supported	36.1%	18.8%	22.6%	20.3%	2.3%
CBE should only be done by female physician	17.3%	11.3%	37.6%	26.3%	7.5%
Overall Attitude	Positive: 54.1%	Negative: 45.9%			

The practice findings also indicate significant knowledge-practice gap as all the students had been educated about BSE, but only 30.8 percent performed it in practice. Lack of knowledge about how to perform BSE (27.8%) and absence of symptoms (33.8%) were the most common reasons not to practice it due to the misconception of BSE prevention. Upon the discovery of abnormalities, a considerable proportion of 33.1 percent visited a health worker, with the other percentages rest with prayer (17.3 percent) or doing nothing (15.8 percent),

representing poor utilization of health workers. The percentage of uptake on clinical breast examination (CBE) was very low standing at 25.6 and mainly lack of awareness and discomfort were the contributing factors to this. The improper practice was noted in 55.6 percent of the respondents, which indicates the necessity of practice training and confidence-building and awareness sessions that will help to diminish the gap between epistemic knowing and acting. [Table 4].

Table 4: Practice of Undergraduate Nurses Towards Breast Cancer

Practice Item	Yes (%)	No (%)
Ever taught BSE (by Doctor/Nurse/Parents/Teacher)	100% (varied sources)	-
Performed BSE	30.8	69.2

Reasons for not practicing BSE	Afraid (17.3%), Lack privacy (13.5%), No symptoms (33.8%), Don't know how (27.8%), Never heard (7.5%)	-
Action taken if an abnormality found during BSE	Prayed (17.3%), Lab test (33.8%), Did nothing (15.8%), Consulted health worker (33.1%)	-
Ever undergone CBE	25.6	74.4
Reasons for not practicing CBE	Expensive (5.3%), Uncomfortable (32.3%), Never heard (45.1%), Embarrassing (17.3%)	-
Overall Practice	Good: 44.4%	Bad: 55.6%

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that the overall knowledge of female undergraduate nursing students regarding breast cancer was low to moderate, with a considerable proportion of participants demonstrating gaps in their understanding of risk factors, symptoms, and treatment options. This aligns with the results of Sarker et al. (2022), who found that undergraduate students in Bangladesh displayed limited knowledge of breast cancer despite being part of the healthcare system. Similarly, Alshahrani et al. (2019) reported poor awareness levels of risk factors such as family history and lifestyle choices among female students, reflecting the persistent global challenge of inadequate knowledge. However, some variations were noted in the current study, as a relatively higher proportion of participants identified treatment methods like radiotherapy and chemotherapy compared to other settings where treatment knowledge was nearly absent.

The findings further demonstrated that a significant number of participants relied on media, books, and lectures as their primary sources of information on breast cancer, which is consistent with Youssif et al. (2023), who observed that nursing students often depend on academic materials and institutional lectures for awareness. In contrast, studies conducted in Ethiopia and Ghana found that healthcare professionals and seminars were more frequently cited as sources of information (Zeru, Sena, & Shaweno, 2019). This discrepancy could be attributed to contextual differences, as in Pakistan, the integration of breast cancer awareness into the formal nursing curriculum may be weaker compared to regions where continuing professional development and community outreach are more emphasized.

The results regarding risk factor awareness showed that a notable proportion of students were unable to identify key contributors such as family history and lifestyle behaviors, with 26.3% reporting "I don't know." This is consistent with a Nigerian study by Yusuf et al. (2022), which highlighted that many nursing students were unaware of critical risk determinants. However, in contrast, Mohebi et al. (2023) demonstrated that Iranian nursing students had relatively higher awareness of genetic and lifestyle-related risks, suggesting regional variations in educational coverage. The limited recognition of modifiable risk factors in the present study is concerning, as this undermines the role of future nurses in promoting prevention strategies.

With regard to the symptoms of breast cancer, the findings revealed poor knowledge overall, as participants failed to consistently recognize common warning signs such as breast mass, nipple discharge, or swelling under the armpit. These results are in line with Odhiambo and Hunter (2023), who found that young women generally had poor recognition of breast cancer symptoms, leading to late presentation and diagnosis. Conversely, Al Thoubaity (2019) reported higher awareness of symptoms among female students in Saudi Arabia, reflecting the success of national awareness campaigns. This contrast emphasizes the need for systematic awareness programs in Pakistan, where cultural taboos and limited access to breast health education continue to hinder knowledge acquisition.

The attitudes of participants in this study presented a mixed picture, with some responses indicating positivity, while others reflected misconceptions or cultural barriers. For example, a large proportion of participants disagreed with the statement that breast cancer screening was unnecessary, suggesting a positive attitude towards screening. These results are

comparable to findings in Ethiopia (Zeru, Sena, & Shaweno, 2019), where students also demonstrated generally positive attitudes despite limited knowledge. However, cultural and religious beliefs continued to serve as barriers, with some participants finding screening embarrassing or unnecessary, a trend also noted in Malaysia (Alaudeen & Ganesan, 2019). This highlights the broader role of social and cultural factors in shaping attitudes towards breast health practices.

The study findings on practice showed poor uptake of preventive behaviors, with only 30.8% of participants practicing breast self-examination (BSE) and 25.6% undergoing clinical breast examination (CBE). This finding mirrors Alaudeen and Ganesan (2019), who also reported low practice rates of BSE and CBE among female students in Malaysia due to embarrassment, lack of privacy, and insufficient knowledge. On the other hand, Yusuf et al. (2022) observed higher practice rates of BSE among Nigerian students, suggesting that educational interventions in certain contexts can yield more favorable outcomes. The similarity between the current study and other Asian contexts highlights the pressing need for culturally sensitive awareness campaigns and training for nursing students.

Overall, the results of this study underscore the critical gaps in knowledge, attitude, and practice among undergraduate nursing students, despite their role as future frontline healthcare providers. The findings are consistent with international literature that identifies nursing students as a population with moderate awareness but poor preventive practices, influenced heavily by cultural beliefs, lack of structured training, and misconceptions (Sarker et al., 2022; Alaudeen & Ganesan, 2019; Zeru, Sena, & Shaweno, 2019). These results collectively suggest that without structured educational interventions, future nurses may be ill-prepared to educate the public, which could perpetuate delayed detection and poor outcomes in breast cancer care. Therefore, integrating comprehensive breast cancer education into nursing curricula and addressing cultural barriers should be prioritized in Pakistan's healthcare education system.

Conclusion

The study assessed the knowledge, attitude, and practice of female undergraduate nursing students regarding breast cancer and found that while some participants had exposure to information through books, lectures, and media, overall knowledge remained low to moderate, particularly concerning risk factors, symptoms, and treatment options. Attitudes toward breast cancer were mixed, with a majority showing positivity toward the importance of screening, though cultural, religious, and social barriers continued to influence perceptions. Practices were found to be weak, with limited adoption of breast self-examination and clinical breast examination, largely due to fear, embarrassment, and lack of knowledge. These findings highlight critical gaps in awareness and preventive behaviors among nursing students, who are expected to be frontline advocates of health education. Without targeted interventions, such gaps may hinder the ability of future nurses to effectively promote early detection and reduce the burden of breast cancer in Pakistan.

Recommendations

Curriculum Integration: Breast cancer education should be formally integrated into undergraduate nursing curricula with emphasis on risk factors, symptoms, prevention, and screening practices.

Practical Training: Workshops and skill-based training sessions on breast self-examination (BSE) and clinical breast examination (CBE) should be made mandatory to strengthen practical competence.

Awareness Campaigns: Nursing institutions should organize regular seminars, awareness drives, and peer-education sessions to dispel misconceptions and reduce stigma associated with breast cancer.

Cultural Sensitization: Educational strategies must address cultural and religious barriers by involving community leaders and using culturally sensitive communication approaches.

Access to Resources: Provision of accessible information through hospital rotations, health camps, and collaboration with NGOs can enhance exposure and understanding of breast cancer prevention.

Policy-Level Interventions: Policymakers should develop national guidelines for breast cancer awareness in nursing education, ensuring that future nurses are equipped to disseminate accurate knowledge.

Further Research: Additional studies are recommended across different regions of Pakistan to explore broader patterns of knowledge, attitudes, and practices among nursing students and practicing nurses.

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